

DIGITAL ECONOMY IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS.

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Abstract: Humanity is experiencing an important period associated with the transformation of economic sectors, digitization, mobilization of this process, and the introduction of artificial intelligence into the field. By 2022, almost a quarter of the world's GDP is projected to be in the digital sector, making the need to develop a new economy even clearer. In developed countries, the implementation of the digital economy has already begun. In the conditions of the globalization of the world economy and the development of technologies, the economic development of Uzbekistan cannot be achieved without the development of the digital economy.

Keywords: GDP, IRR, NPV, artificial intelligence, smart economy, e-business, e-commerce.

The implementation of electronic government elements and support of the digital economy have a strong place in Uzbekistan's near-term development plan. First of all, this concerns the tasks of further increasing the share of electronic document exchange and gradually transferring a certain part of state services to electronic form through State Service Centers. Telecommunications infrastructure plays an important role in this process.

Interest in the digital economy has grown significantly due to significant changes in society and the economy. Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals reduce costs by minimizing personal interactions with customers, partners, and government organizations, as well as making communication faster and easier. The result is a digital or electronic economy based on network resources.

The word "digitalization" is actually a new term, which refers to the involvement of IT solutions in the process of innovative management and administration, and as a result, the use of information technologies in all systems, from Internet of Things to e-government.

The main source of the digital segment of the economy is the growth of the transactional sector. In developed countries, this indicator makes up more than 70 percent of GDP and combines public administration, consulting and information services, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as services (utility, personal and social).

The higher the diversification and dynamics of the economy, the greater the circulation of unique information within and outside the country, and the greater the information traffic within national economies. Therefore, the digital economy develops rapidly in markets where the number of participants is large and IT services are widespread.

According to the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030"¹ Strategy, artificial intelligence technologies are being rapidly adopted and widely used in our nation. We are facilitating access to high-quality digital data and creating suitable conditions for the training of talented professionals in this field. The decision was approved by the president in order to establish the requirements, and as a result, the following was authorized. The primary objective was to create a plan for the advancement of artificial intelligence that outlines the major directions and guiding principles for its application as well as the prerequisites for the comprehensive formation of this subject in the short- and long-term. creation of a regulatory legal framework that spells out standardized conditions, accountability, security, and transparency in the creation and use of artificial intelligence. The primary objective was to create a plan for the advancement of artificial intelligence that outlines the major directions and guiding principles for its application as well as the prerequisites for the comprehensive formation of this subject in the short- and long-term. the creation of a regulatory legal framework that outlines uniform standards for accountability, responsibility, security, and transparency in the development and use of artificial intelligence technologies in economic and social spheres, in state administration system, as well as widespread use of artificial intelligence technologies to enhance the quality of public services in the interests of the population, as well as to increase the efficiency of state bodies in data processing construction of a local ecosystem for cutting-edge advances in artificial intelligence, supporting their transfer and ensuing commercialization; and setting up the right environment for software developers to leverage digital data while developing their products, Along with ensuring quick digitization of pertinent data from government agencies and organizations, scientific advancements in the field of artificial intelligence are needed to create an investment climate that is attractive to investors. This includes increasing the competitiveness of goods (works and services) in both domestic and international markets and giving local businesses and experts access to information sources and knowledge in the field of artificial intelligence significant insights and trends are revealed by a thorough analysis of the

¹ On Measures For Creating Conditions for Accelerated Implementation of Artificial Intelligence Technologies PQ-4996 02.27.2021

pertinent literature on the effects of artificial intelligence (AI) on the digital economy. The summary that follows highlights several important research findings: **Increased Productivity and Efficiency:** AI technologies like automation and machine learning have the potential to greatly increase productivity and efficiency in a variety of digital economy industries. AI-driven algorithms can quickly and accurately evaluate enormous amounts of data, allowing organizations to make better decisions and streamline their processes. **Workforce implications of job transformation.** The use of AI technologies may result in job shifts, with new job positions and possibilities emerging as some functions are automated. Despite the possibility of some occupations being replaced, studies show that overall, AI may enhance human capabilities, resulting in better job quality and the development of new jobs. **Economic Growth and Innovation:** AI has the potential to promote innovation in the digital economy and fuel economic growth. It makes it possible to create brand-new goods and services, spot untapped market niches, and enhance client satisfaction. The ethical and societal ramifications of AI in the digital economy have received a great deal of attention in the literature. There has been much discussion about privacy issues, algorithmic unfairness, the effect of AI on social inequality, and employment displacement. **Policy and Regulation:** According to the literature, it is crucial to establish suitable laws and regulations that will oversee the moral and responsible use of AI in the digital economy. The focus is mostly on issues like data privacy, algorithmic transparency, and AI governance frameworks. **Impacts on a Particular Sector:** Different facets of the digital economy are affected by AI differently.

It includes the automation of routine tasks, augmenting human capabilities, driving innovation, and creating new job opportunities. The evolving nature of work in the digital age necessitates individuals to adapt, upskill, and focus on areas where human skills are uniquely valuable. Embracing AI as a collaborative tool and harnessing its potential can lead to greater productivity, efficiency, and innovation, ultimately shaping the purpose of work in the digital economy.

2Figure 1. Revenues from the global market of AI from 2016 to 2025, million \$

Statistics show that in the period 2016-2019 revenues of the world market for AI increased by 350%, from 3221.8 to \$ 11283.76 million (Figure 1). By 2025, revenues are expected to rise to \$ 89847.26 million.

With Digital economy infrastructure becoming more capable of processing and delivering accurate solutions, the involvement of AI in the transportation and automotive industry will only increase in the future.

Table 1

Digital economy infrastructure becoming more capable of processing and delivering accurate solutions

Territories	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	In 2021 to 2015
Republic of Uzbekistan	223927	271257	310459	358003	413417	441913	538933	240,7
Republic of Karakalpakstan	9372	10692	12594	15431	17788	21882	23958	255,6
Andijan	7950	8839	11972	14699	17830	20173	22450	282,4
Bukhara	9963	12	14073	1604	1951	23101	2866	287,7

²S.V. Novikov,A.A. Sazonov,C. C. Ortíz Paez: Artificial intelligence as a focus of digital economy development: Theoretical and practical aspects.
<https://economicsjournal.info/index.php/edu/article/view>

		565		1	3		6	
Jizzakh	9257	11 796	12 822	14 20 0	14 82 2	9 251	19 92 4	215,2
Kashkadarya	6430	11 49 1	13 179	14 85 7	18 00 6	18 631	27 57 3	428,8
Navoi	8516	10 40 3	11 190	14 49 0	17 68 6	18 246	21 02 5	246,9
Namangan	6615	8 942	10 499	13 80 0	17 29 2	20 408	22 96 0	347,1
Samarkand	12803	16 77 5	23 569	26 95 5	32 00 1	33 970	39 36 7	307,5
Surkhandarya	4728	5 561	6 907	8 611	9 323	8 840	14 50 9	306,9
Syrdarya	3961	4 542	5 488	6 327	7 849	10 245	12 75 3	322,0
Tashkent	12695	15 48 4	18 371	23393	29 22 8	36 050	45 03 1	354,7
Ferghana	10 833	14 03 5	15 489	18 44 9	21 50 8	27 590	32 63 8	301,3
Khorezm	7 533	8 578	9 410	11 96 2	14 81 1	17 600	20 29 7	269,4
Tashkent city	113 251	131 654	144 89 6	158 7 88	175 7 60	175 92 6	207 782	183,5

Figure-2 , Number of computers connected to the Internet at enterprises and organizations (at the end of the year, units)³

Digital economy is an economic activity based on digital technologies, connected with e-business, e-commerce, producing and providing digital goods and services. In this case, payments for economic services and goods are made through electronic money. The concept of the digital economy is based on the transition from atom to bit, that is, from the smallest chemical particle to an electronic unit.

The digital economy makes it possible to increase the efficiency of large-scale industrial facilities, increase production, ensure transparency of activity, and reduce product costs. GDP will increase by 30 percent.

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